

THE EFFECT OF THERMOPLASTIC ADDITIVES AND CARBON FIBRES ON THE THERMALLY ENHANCED MOISTURE ABSORPTION BY EPOXY RESINS

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SUMMARY: The moisture absorption of the base resin, polyether sulphone (PES) modified blend and carbon fibre composite under isothermal and thermal spiking conditions has been examined. The addition of PES reduced proportionally the moisture in the isothermally conditioned coupons but not for those thermally spiked. The maximum enhancement temperature of 140°C, was a function of the base epoxy resin. A secondary relaxation peak (T_{g2}) developed at a significantly lower temperature than the main relaxation. For the PES modified epoxy resin, thermal spiking did not reduce T_{g2} below that for the isothermally conditioned sample. However, in the presence of carbon fibres, T_{g2} was sensitive to thermal spiking, indicating an interphasal component to the moisture mechanisms.

KEYWORDS: thermal spiking, moisture absorption, polyether sulphone, epoxy resin, carbon fibre composites

INTRODUCTION

Epoxy resins are the most common matrices for high performance carbon-fibre composites because of the ease with which the curing process can be controlled. However they readily absorb moisture usually resulting in lower strength and softening temperature. Certain aircraft components can be exposed to temperatures in excess of 100°C for only a few minutes [1]. Under conditions of rapid heating and cooling, the moisture absorption of epoxy/carbon laminates can be increased significantly [2-4], over that for hygrothermal conditions. The mechanisms of enhanced moisture absorption as a result of a thermal spike are unclear.

In this paper, the effect of the polyether sulphone (PES) thermoplastic modifier on the thermally enhanced moisture absorption of an epoxy resin system has been studied..

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

The system chosen was the Fibredux 924 laminate system from Ciba Geigy. This is a diaminodiphenylsulphone cured TGDDM epoxy resin with added polyethersulphone (PES) thermoplastic. The manufacturer provided the base epoxy resin without added PES (924E),

and cast tape of resin containing the commercial concentration of PES (924T), which is used for fibre impregnation. The finished prepreg tape was also supplied. To obtain resin samples of varying PES concentration, the base 924E resin was blended with different weight fractions of the modified 924T resin at 100°C. The actual concentration of PES is unknown for commercial reasons, (Table 1).

Table 1: Resin Blends with relative PES concentration

Resin System Under Study	PES concentration as a percentage of the commercial content)
924E	0
924/¼T	25%
924/½T	50%
924/¾T	75%
924T	100%
924C (composite)	100%

The base resin, commercial resin and blends, were degassed at 110°C for 1.5 hours, poured into a mould and degassed for a further 0.5 hours. The resins were then cured in a press-clave under a nitrogen atmosphere at a pressure of 700 KN/m². The recommended cure cycle was as follows; heat from room temperature at 2°C/min to 130°C, dwell for 2.5 hours, heat at 1°C/min to 180°C, dwell for 2 hours, then cool to room temperature at less than 3°C/min. For the 924C system, the prepreg tape was cut to the required dimensions and stacked to form an 8-ply laminate which was cured in a press-clave for 2 hours at 180°C, using recommended vacuum bagging procedures and cure cycles.

Conditioning

For conditioning, the 924 resin samples were cut to dimensions of 60 by 30 mm using a water cooled diamond saw, whilst 924C composite samples were cut to dimensions of 20 by 140 mm. The resin coupons were then milled to a thickness of 1mm. The edges of all samples were polished to a 1200 grit finish prior to post-curing at 180°C for 2 hours. The coupons were dried to constant weight in a vacuum oven at 50°C, and placed on racks above a saturated salt solution of potassium sulphate (K₂SO₄) in distilled water, in a sealed humidity chamber held at 50°C in an air-circulating oven to provide a relative humidity of 96%. The coupons were removed intermittently, weighed and returned to the humidity chamber (control samples) or subjected to a thermal spike (spiked specimens). After spiking, they were reweighed and replaced in the environment. Sorption curves were plotted as moisture content, M_t in weight percent, against \sqrt{time} . The weight changes were determined using an electro-balance accurate to 10⁻⁵ g.

Thermal Spike Program

Coupons were placed in metal racks, to ensure both major surfaces were heated evenly, and placed in an air-circulating oven pre-heated to the spike temperature. Time spent at the spike

temperature was calculated so that the specimen was maintained at this temperature for 1 minute. Table 2 lists the spiking times for 924 8-ply laminates.

For consistency, the same spike times were used for the 1mm thick un-reinforced resin specimens. The samples were and allowed to cool before replacement in the conditioning chambers.

Table 2: The time spent in the spike oven for samples spiked to between 100 and 200°C.

Thermal Spike Temperature (°C)	Spike Time for O ₈ 924 laminates and resin coupons (min.)
100	3.5
120	4
140	4.5
160	5
180	5.5
200	6

Thermomechanical Analysis

Dynamic Mechanical Thermal Analysis (DMTA) was performed in dual cantilever bending mode using a Polymer Laboratories Mk II analyser. This allowed the effect of thermal spiking and enhanced moisture absorption on the viscoelastic properties, such as the glass transition temperature to be measured. Samples of dimensions 10 by 40 mm were cut from the conditioned specimens. For 924C samples, the fibres were at 90°C to the DMTA clamp faces. A frequency of 1Hz was used over a temperature of 50°C to 300°C.

RESULTS

Fig. 1 shows the moisture absorption curves for the 140°C spiked and control O₈-924C coupons. For the 140°C spike curve, the peaks correspond to the moisture content prior to a thermal spike, and the troughs correspond to the moisture content after a thermal spike. Moisture is lost during the thermal spike. For simplicity the moisture content after a thermal spike is omitted from subsequent plots of moisture absorption.

Figs. 2-4 show the moisture absorption curves for coupons of 924E resin, 924T epoxy/PES resin, and 924C composite respectively. These were subjected to 22 spikes to between 100°C and 200°C, and 5000 hours conditioning.. The first 4 points on the curves are of the same value since the samples have not been spiked. Thus the fourth point on the curves represents the moisture content prior to the first spike. It can be seen that spikes as low as 100°C result in an increased moisture concentration, in all three systems.

The moisture concentration of the spiked samples exceeds that of the control samples after the first spike (i.e. the fifth point on the curves). Maximum moisture enhancement occurs in samples spiked to 140°C. Spiking above this temperature results in lower moisture absorption. After 5000 hours and 22 spikes, an equilibrium moisture content has not been reached for the resin systems, since moisture concentration is still increasing. This is also true of the unspiked control resin specimens. The sorption curves for the 924C laminates show lower rates of absorption than their resin counterparts, however equilibrium is still not reached after 5000 hours and 22 spikes. The highest rate of absorption was observed between the first and seventh spike for resin and composite coupons spiked to 160°C. After 12 spikes, the 140°C spiked coupons absorb moisture at the highest rate.

Fig.1: The effect of thermal spikes to 140°C on the moisture absorption of 924C-0₈ laminates conditioned at 50°C/96% R.H

Fig.2: Moisture absorption curves for 924E epoxy resin after 5000 hours conditioning & 22 thermal spikes

Fig.3: Moisture absorption curves for 924T epoxy/PES resin after 5000 hours conditioning & 22 thermal spikes. [See Fig 2 for key]

Table 3 lists the final moisture contents of 924E, 924T resins, and 924C composite samples after 22 thermal spikes and over 5000 hours conditioning. Since moisture absorption is a matrix dominated property and the matrix volume fraction is approximately 35% of the composite, normalised values for the matrix moisture absorption in the 924C composite are also presented. That is moisture contents are multiplied by 2.86, to calculate the moisture concentration in the matrix alone. The normalised 924C value for moisture concentration in matrix alone was 4.92 wt.%. The moisture concentration increases in the order 924C<924T<924E, for each spike temperature. However, the normalised values for 924C samples approximately equal those of the 924T resin alone. Thermal spikes to 140°C, the maximum moisture enhancement temperature, result in moisture concentrations of 9.66, 9.20, 2.98 wt.% in the 924E, 924T and 924C systems respectively.

Table 3: Final moisture concentrations in 924E, 924T resins and 924C laminates

Spike Temp (°C)	Moisture Content after 22 spikes & 5000 hours conditioning wt.%			
	924E (no PES)	924T (with PES)	924C	924C (normalised)
isothermal/50	6.95	5.32	1.72	4.92
100	7.57	6.22	2.37	6.78
120	9.20	7.75	2.84	8.12
140	9.66	9.20	2.98	8.52
160	9.06	8.26	2.88	8.24
180	8.33	6.88	2.43	6.95
200	7.27	6.32	2.08	5.95

This represents an increase relative to the isothermal moisture concentrations, of 39% for the 924E resin, and an increase of 73% for the 924T resin and 924C composite containing PES. Fig. 5 shows the moisture concentrations plotted as a function of spike temperature of all 3 systems and the normalised matrix moisture concentration in the 924C laminates. It is seen that a maximum moisture enhancement temperature exists at 140°C for all systems.

Under isothermal conditions the 924E base resin absorbed 6.95 wt.% moisture, while 924T toughened resin absorbed 5.32 wt.% moisture, and the 924C laminates absorbed 1.72 wt.%, which was the lowest moisture concentration.

Resin samples of differing PES content, as listed in Table 1, were conditioned for over 4000 hours, and subjected to 18 thermal spikes to 140°C or 160°C. The absorption curves for these samples were similar in appearance to those for the isothermal 140°C and 160°C spiked 924E and 924T resin specimens shown in Figs. 2 & 3. Table 4 lists the moisture concentrations

after 4000 hours conditioning at 96% R.H., and 18 thermal spikes for 924 resin specimens containing 1/4, 1/2, 3/4 of the commercial amount of PES.

Fig.4: Moisture absorption curves for 924C-O₈ composite after 5000 hours conditioning & 22 thermal spikes

Fig.5: Moisture concentration against spike temperature, for 924E, 924T & 924C samples after 5000 hours conditioning & 22 spikes

Table 4: Final moisture concentrations for 924 resin samples of varying PES content

Spike temperature (°C)	Moisture Content after 4000 hours conditioning and 18 thermal spikes (wt.%)				
	924E	924/1/4T	924/1/2T	924/3/4T	924T
isothermal/50	6.40	6.13	6.68	6.77	5.05
140	9.27	8.98	9.13	8.76	9.00
160	8.67	8.39	8.18	7.99	8.20

The enhanced moisture absorption phenomenon is unaffected by PES content, and occurs in all samples when thermally spiked to 140°C or 160°C. The maximum moisture enhancement temperature of 140°C, is in agreement with that for the 924C composite. A Thermal spike temperature of 160°C results in the fastest initial moisture uptake, for all levels of PES. This data is plotted against the relative PES content in Fig. 6. As already shown in Fig. 5, under isothermal conditions the moisture concentration in 924T samples is approximately 20% less than in the 924E base epoxy resin. However moisture concentrations in resin formulations of intermediate PES content do not follow any clear trend. Under isothermal conditions, the 924/3/4T samples containing 75% of the commercial amount of PES contain the highest moisture concentration at 6.77 wt.%.

Figure 7, illustrates schematically the effect of thermal spiking and moisture absorption on the DMTA $\tan\delta$ and storage modulus, $\log E'$, curves for the resins and laminates. The traces shown are for a dry as-cured sample, an isothermally conditioned sample, and a thermally spiked sample. The primary $\tan\delta$ peak, T_{g1} , which was observed for the as-cured/dry samples, fell slightly on isothermal moisture absorption. A secondary peak, T_{g2} , emerged in all wet specimens. This peak was least prominent for the 924E samples, compared to 924T epoxy/PES samples. The intensity of the T_{g2} peak was greatest and shifted to lower temperatures in 924C laminates samples after moisture absorption and thermal spiking, relative to the two resin systems. It can be seen that the temperature at which the slope of the storage modulus, $\log E'$, curve begins to decrease rapidly, termed the glass transition onset, $T_{gE'}$, is reduced on isothermal moisture absorption. This is further reduced when the laminates are thermally spiked.

Fig. 8a) & b) plots of T_{g1} and T_{g2} for samples conditioned for over 5000 hours against thermal spike temperature. It is seen that T_{g1} for 924C laminates, is approximately 15° to 20°C lower than for the 924E and 924T resin systems. Isothermal moisture absorption reduces T_{g1} by approximately 10°C for each system. Thermal spikes to 100°C further reduce T_{g1} only slightly in the 924C and 924T samples to 239°C and 217°C respectively, but do not effect T_{g1} in 924 samples which remains at approximately 240°C. Thermal spikes to 120°C and above do not significantly reduce T_{g1} any further. For the dry systems, one relaxation peak was observed. However on isothermal moisture absorption a secondary relaxation peak, T_{g2} , emerges for all three systems, at a temperature between 174°C and 189°C. Thermal spiking to 100°C reduces T_{g2} further by 22°C in 924 laminates, but is unaffected in the 924E and 924T resin samples. Thermal spikes to 120°C and above does not reduce T_{g2} further.

Fig.6: Moisture content in 924 resin samples of differing PES content after 4000 hours conditioning at 96% R.H., and 18 spikes

Fig.7: Schematic illustration of the effect of moisture absorption and thermal spiking on the DMTA relaxation spectra, $\tan \delta$, and the storage modulus, $\log E'$, in 924 systems

Fig.8: Changes in DMTA a) primary and b) secondary $\tan \delta$ peaks with thermal spike temperature for 924E, 924T resin and 924C laminate systems

Fig. 9 shows how the glass transition onset temperature, $T_{gE'}$, changes with thermal spike temperature, for the three systems. It is seen that the dry/ as-cured $T_{gE'}$ is 225°C for the 924E resin, 201°C for the 924T resin, and 207°C for the 924C laminate. Isothermal absorption of moisture results in a $T_{gE'}$ of 160°, 168° and 152°C for the 924E, 924T and 924C systems respectively. Thermal spikes to 100°C reduce $T_{gE'}$ further in the 924T and 924C systems to 153°C and 135°C respectively, whereas $T_{gE'}$ for the 924E base epoxy is relatively unaffected. Thermal spikes to 120°C and above reduce $T_{gE'}$ of 924C to a minimum of 129°C, 20°C lower than the $T_{gE'}$ of both resin systems which are unaffected.

Fig.9: Changes in glass transition onset temperature, T_{gE} , with thermal spike temperature in 924E, 924T resin and 924C composite systems

DISCUSSION

The absorption curves shown in Figs. 2-4, are non-Fickian for all 3 systems. That is an equilibrium moisture content is not reached, and the initial linear region does not account for 60% of the total moisture absorbed. The addition of PES to the base epoxy resin, reduces the concentration of moisture absorbed under isothermal conditions by approximately 20%. The weight fraction of PES in the 924T commercial resin is considered to be approximately 18 wt.%, hence this can be explained simply by the lower moisture absorption of the PES component. The addition of carbon fibres, reduces the moisture concentration by a further 65%. As shown in Fig. 5 the moisture concentration in 924C laminates when normalised to the volume fraction of matrix, are close to that of the 924T resin-only samples. Thermal spiking results in an increased moisture concentration for all three systems. The 924E base epoxy samples absorbed the most moisture, where the 924T resin and normalised 924C composite values were approximately equal. Suggesting that the addition of carbon fibres has a minimal effect on the enhanced moisture absorption phenomena. At the maximum moisture enhancement temperature of 140°C, the moisture concentration is increased by approximately 40% in the 924E samples. In the 924T samples, the increase was 73%, to a concentration close to that of the 924E base epoxy system. Normalised data for the 924C composite showed a 73% increase to similar values. This implies that the addition of PES to the base epoxy reduces the amount of moisture absorbed under isothermal conditions, but when thermally spiked to 140°C, the difference is less prominent..

Fig. 5 shows that the enhanced moisture absorption is greatest for the base epoxy resin, and that the addition of PES and reinforcing carbon fibres does not affect this significantly. Microscopic examination of the spiked samples did not show any significant damage such as microcracks, voids or delaminations in the composite, confirming that the additional moisture must reside in the polymer network on a molecular level [5]. Analysis of absorption curves for the resin samples with intermediate PES content, show that changing the weight fraction of PES does not alter the enhanced moisture absorption phenomena, and that the maximum

moisture enhancement spike temperature remains at 140°C (Fig.6). Specimens spiked to this temperature contained between 30 to 45% more moisture than the isothermally conditioned specimens. However the moisture concentration did not decrease significantly with increasing PES content. Since this is an assumption behind the blending technology it is clear that the maximum moisture content after thermal spiking is not a simple dilution of the most moisture sensitive component. However the mixing procedure employed in the laboratory may differ from that used commercially so that the homogeneity of the cured resin-blends may differ from the commercial systems. Thus the re-distribution of unoccupied volume into free volume of molecular size and microvoids of larger dimensions could be affected.

In Fig. 7 it is seen that the secondary relaxation peak Tg_2 is most sensitive to thermally enhanced moisture absorption. This suggests that the water may plasticise one component in the polymer network more efficiently. Water present in a polymer network is often considered to be present in the free volume where it interrupts the attractive forces acting between polar structures in the network [6], leading to plasticisation. Thus at high moisture concentrations a greater depression of Tg is predicted. This is true for isothermal absorption. However moisture absorbed through thermal spiking does not appear to plasticise the polymer further. It is evident from Fig.8b that the addition of PES to the base epoxy results in a larger reduction in Tg_2 on moisture absorption. The implication of this result is that the PES phase modifies the susceptibility of the epoxy resin network to plasticisation by water. However, an alternative explanation could revolve around the dimensions of the unoccupied volume. It is also evident that the addition of carbon fibres reduces Tg_1 and Tg_2 even further. The reasons for this are not clear, but one possible cause may be the presence of a sizing resin on the fibres which is usually epoxy based, and may combine with the matrix resin to form a cured region of lower glass transition temperature (i.e. an interphase).

CONCLUSIONS

The enhanced moisture absorption which results from thermal spiking is shown to be a function of the epoxy resin. Thermal spiking of 924E epoxy-only resin, epoxy/PES resin and 924C laminates conditioned in humid environments, increased the rates and concentrations of moisture absorbed. Maximum moisture enhancement occurs at a spike temperature of 140°C. The addition of the thermoplastic PES and carbon fibres to the epoxy matrix reduced the total moisture absorbed under isothermal conditions. However, the enhanced moisture absorption was unaffected under thermal spiking. A secondary relaxation peak appears in the $\text{Tan } \delta$ curves for the wet resin and composites. Tg_2 appears at the lowest temperature and with greatest intensity for the composite. The non-modified base epoxy resin was the least susceptible. Thus the addition of PES and carbon fibres appears to increase the susceptibility of the bulk resin to plasticisation under isothermal conditions. The extra moisture absorbed as a result of thermal spiking does not shift this secondary peak to lower temperatures. The moisture is resident in the polymer network, rather than in thermally induced voids or microcracks. Moisture can be accommodated in the free volume of a polymer network, where the interactions between polar groups are displaced. This results in a reduction in glass transition temperature. However this study indicates that the extra moisture as a result of thermal spiking does not plasticise the polymer material in this manner. The enhanced moisture absorption in thermally spiked epoxy resins is unaffected by the addition of the PES modifier. Only the total moisture absorbed is affected. The softening point of 924C laminates is reduced by thermal spikes of 100°C and above to well within the 'Hot/Wet' maximum service temperature stated by the manufacturers.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We are indebted to DRA, Farnborough for financial support, Ciba Geigy plc, Duxford for the resins.

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